

THE MAIN PECULARITIES OF THE NOVEL “THE THIRD LIFE OF GRANGE COPELAND” BY ALICE WALKER

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ABSTRACT

Alice Walker's novels are popular for their expressions of the Black woman's life. One of them is the novel of The Third Life of Grange Copeland that She focuses on vividly the sexism, racism, and poverty that often make that life a struggle. But she also portrays, as part of that life, the strengths of family, community, self-worth, and spirituality. Many of her novels depict women in other periods of history than our own.

The story of Alice Walker's childhood scar provides the most basic metaphor of her novels: the idea that radical change is possible even under the worst conditions. Although she was never able to regain the sight in one eye, Walker's disfigurement was considerably lessened: I used to pray every night that I would wake up and somehow it would be gone. I couldn't look at people directly because I thought I was ugly. . . . Then when I was fourteen, I visited my brother Bill [who] took me to a hospital where they removed most of the scar tissue and I was a *changed person*. I promptly went home, scooped up the best-looking guy, and by the time I graduated from high school, I was valedictorian, voted "Most Popular," and crowned queen!

The idea that change and personal triumph are possible despite the odds is central to all of Walker's writing. Her work focuses directly or indirectly on the ways of survival adopted by black women, usually in the South, and is presented in a prose style characterized by a distinctive combination of lyricism and unflinching realism. Walker's women attempt not merely to survive, but to survive completely with some sense of stability, despite the constant thread of family violence, physical and mental abuse, and a lack of responsibility on the part of the men in their lives. Walker is simultaneously a feminist and a supporter of civil rights, not only for black Americans but also for minorities everywhere.

Walker's vision was shaped in part by a work from the first flowering of black writing in America: Jean Toomer's *Cane* (1923). She said in 1974 about Toomer's book that "it has been reverberating in me to an astonishing degree. *I love it passionately*; could not possibly exist without it." Like *Cane*, the first part of which centers mainly on women in the South, Walker's novels are made up of nearly equal parts of poetry, portraiture, and drama, broken up into a series of sections and subsections. Other important literary influences on Walker include Zora Neale Hurston, from whom she inherited a love of black folklore; Flannery

O'Connor, who wrote of southern violence and grotesqueries from her home in Milledgeville, Georgia, fewer than ten miles from Walker's childhood home; and Albert Camus, whose existentialism speaks to the struggle for survival and dignity in which Walker's characters are engaged. Walker herself defined her "preoccupations" as a novelist: "The survival, the survival *whole* of my people. But beyond that I am committed to exploring the oppressions, the insanities, the loyalties, and the triumphs of black women."

The Third Life of Grange Copeland, on the surface a novel about the cycle of rage and violence torturing the lives of a father and his son, is as much about the recipients of that rage the women and children whose lives are directly affected. Although the novel is unremitting in its picture of desperate poverty's legacy of hatred, hopelessness, and cruelty, it concludes optimistically with Ruth Copeland's hope for a release from sorrow through the redemption promised by the early days of the Civil Rights movement and by the knowledge and love inherited at the sacrificial death of her grandfather.

The Third Life of Grange Copeland

Writing in 1973, Walker observed that her first novel, *The Third Life of Grange Copeland*, "though sometimes humorous and celebrative of life, is a grave book in which the characters see the world as almost entirely menacing." This dark view of life is common to Grange Copeland, the patriarch of a family farming on shares in rural Georgia, his son Brownfield, and the wives and daughters of both men. For all these characters, the world is menacing because of the socioeconomic position they occupy at the bottom of the scale of the sharecropping system. Father and son menace each other in this novel because they are in turn menaced by rage born out of the frustration of the system. Although the white people of the book are nearly always vague, nameless, and impersonal, they and the system they represent have the ability to render both Grange and Brownfield powerless.

It is not accidental that these characters' names have agricultural connotations. "Grange" suggests a late nineteenth century association of farmers, a feudal farm and grain storage building, and a combination of graze and range, while "Brownfield" and "Copeland" are self-explanatory for the inability to cope with the land is what leads both male characters along virtually parallel paths. For the father, the mere appearance of the white farm boss's truck is enough to turn his face "into a unnaturally bland mask, curious and unsettling to see." The appearance of the truck causes the son to be "filled with terror of this man who could, by his presence alone, turn his father into something that might as well have been a pebble or a post or a piece of dirt." Although Grange is, in this same image, literally a piece of land, he eventually returns to the South and learns to live self-sufficiently, farming a section of soil he tricked his second wife into giving to him. Brownfield, in contrast, is never able to escape from the sharecropping system, although he sees that, like his father, he is "destined to be no more than overseer, on the white man's plantation, of his own children." Brownfield is able to live obliviously on a farm in Georgia, content to blame all of his problems on others. The poor rural black workers of this novel are themselves little more than a crop, rotated from farm to farm, producing a harvest of shame and hunger, cruelty and violence.

Unlike the men of the novel, the women are menaced by both black and white people, by both the agricultural system and the "strange fruit" it produces. Margaret, Grange's first wife, is both physically and mentally degraded by her husband and then sexually exploited by a white truck driver, resulting in her second pregnancy. Unable to cope with this situation,

Grange deserts his family, after which his wife poisons both her child and herself. Following his father's pattern, Brownfield marries and begins to work the land, but after "a year when endless sunup to sundown work on fifty rich bottom acres of cotton land and a good crop brought them two diseased shoats for winter meat." he too begins to abuse his wife. Although Brownfield's wife, Mem, is a schoolteacher intelligent enough to try to break the cycle of raising other people's crops, her brief rebellion against her husband's malevolent beatings and mental tortures is a failure: He is able to subjugate her through repeated pregnancies that sap her rebellion as they turn her once rich and strong body into a virtual wasteland of emaciation. Because her body, which represents the land of the South, is still able to produce children despite its depleted condition, Brownfield is enraged enough to murder her in retaliation for her physical shape: "he had murdered his wife because she had become skinny and had not, with much irritation to him, reverted, even when well-fed, to her former plumpness. . . . Plumpness and freedom from the land, from cows and skinniness, went all together in his mind." Despite his irrational abuse of her, Mem is not ashamed "of being black though, no matter what he said. . . . Color was something the ground did to the flowers, and that was an end to it."

What the ground did to these generations of southern black people is the subject of Walker's novel the whole lurid history of violence, hatred, and guilt that she chronicles in this story of one family's griefs. By the book's end, Brownfield Copeland has murdered his wife and an unnamed albino baby, while Grange Copeland has murdered his son Brownfield first spiritually, then physically and indirectly has killed his first wife and her infant.

Walker's characters are allegorical representations of the classic modes of survival historically adopted by black Americans in dealing with their oppression. Brownfield identifies with whites by daydreaming of himself on a southern plantation, sipping mint juleps, and then by bargaining for his freedom with the sexual favors of black women. Both of Grange's wives attempt to be true to the white stereotype of black women as promiscuous sexual beings, free of any moral restraints. Brownfield's wife, Mem, attempts the passive resistance advocated by Martin Luther King, Jr., but she is destroyed by what her husband calls "her weakness . . . forgiveness, a stupid belief that kindness can convert the enemy." Brownfield's daughter, Daphne, who calls herself the Copeland Family Secret Keeper, tries the strategy of inventing a falsely romantic history of the past, of the good old days when her father was kind, echoing those historical revisionists who try to argue that slavery was not that bad. Brownfield's other daughters try to stay away from their father altogether, regarding him "as a human devil" of whom they were afraid "in a more distant, impersonal way. He was like bad weather, a toothache, daily bad news."

Each of the title character's three lives (at home in the South as a sharecropper married to Margaret; in the North as a hustler of alcohol, drugs, and women; and finally back in the South as a farmer married to Josie and rearing his granddaughter Ruth) parallels a traditional survival strategy, which Grange summarizes as follows, "The white folks hated me and I hated myself until I started hating them in return and loving myself. Then I tried just loving me, and then you, and *ignoring* them much as I could." To put it another way, Grange tries at first to adapt to the system by believing what whites say about black people; then he turns to the classic escape of the runaway slave heading North to freedom; finally, he tries the technique of praising black life while ignoring whites altogether. A large part of the novel's devastation is

caused by the repeated use of these techniques, not against whites, but against other members of the Copeland family. Only Ruth, the granddaughter through whom Grange seeks redemption, is able to deal with whites in an intelligent, balanced, non-destructive yet independent way. She has learned from her grandfather, and from her family history, that pure hatred becomes self-hatred, and violence begets self-violence; she therefore becomes the novel's symbol of the new black woman, ready to assume her place in black history as a courageous worker in the Civil Rights movement that the rest of her family has been groping to discover.

References:

1. Abdusamatovna, B. N. (2022). WAYS OF DEVELOPING SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 10(12), 690-695.
2. Bo'stonova, N., & Ismoilov, S. (2023, November). O 'ZBEKISTONDA INNOVATSION TADBIRKORLIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH YONALISHLARI. In Conference on Digital Innovation: "Modern Problems and Solutions".
3. Abdusamatovna, B. N. (2023). THE ROLE OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF OUR COUNTRY. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(5).
4. Nurullo, K., & Nafisa, S. (2023). Digitalization-as the main factor in the development of the quality management system of the textiles industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In *BIO Web of Conferences* (Vol. 65, p. 03004). EDP Sciences.
5. Рахманова, А. (2021). О восточных традициях в русской литературе. *АКТУАЛЬНОЕ В ФИЛОЛОГИИ*, 3(3).
6. Рахманова, А. Х. (2021). СИНТЕЗ БИБЛЕЙСКИХ И КОРАНИЧЕСКИХ МОТИВОВ В СТИХОТВОРЕНИИ ПУШКИНА «ПРОРОК». *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(12), 1404-1412.
7. Халилов, Н. Х., & Сафина, Н. Т. (2023). НЕОБХОДИМОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ СИСТЕМЫ МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА КАЧЕСТВА ДЛЯ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ ПРОДУКЦИИ. *SCIENTIFIC ASPECTS AND TRENDS IN THE FIELD OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH*, 1(7), 33-39.
8. Алиева, З. (2024). ЧТО ТАКОЕ «ИННОВАЦИОННОЕ ОБУЧЕНИЕ» И В ЧЁМ ЕГО ОСОБЕННОСТИ. *Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences*, 3(1), 44-47.
9. Алиева, З. Р., & Довудхўжаева, Ш. (2020). ШКОЛА БУДУЩЕГО-НАШИМИ ГЛАЗАМИ. *Студенческий вестник*, (31-1), 6-7.
10. Aliyeva, Z. R. (2022). The concept of historical styling. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(11), 768-784.
11. Khamidillayevich, K. N., & Talgatovna, S. N. (2022). СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ КАЧЕСТВОМ НА ПРЕДПРИЯТИЯХ ЛЁГКОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ УЗБЕКИСТАН. In *Colloquium-journal* (No. 15 (138), pp. 81-83). Голопристанський міськрайонний центр зайнятості.
12. Khalilov, N. K. (2022). Safina. NT "Development of the quality management system of industrial enterprises-the main factor of increasing the competitiveness of products". *World Economics & Finance Bulletin (WEFB)* Available Online at: <https://www.scholarexpress.net>, 12.

13. Халилов, Н., & Сафина, Н. (2022). Цифровизация-как основной фактор развития системы менеджмента качества текстильной промышленности в Республике Узбекистан. №, 13, 136.
14. Talgatovna, S. N., & Rashidbek o'g'li, E. Q. (2023). XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDA STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV MASALALARI. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS, 2(21), 33-42.
15. Зуфарова, Г. А., & Сафина, Н. Т. (2018). Необходимость развития логистики в агропромышленном комплексе Республики Узбекистан. Вестник Донецкой академии автомобильного транспорта, (1), 23-28.
16. Abduraximova, T. (2023). BOLONIYA JARAYONINING GENEZISI VA EVOLYUTSIYASI. Namangan davlat universiteti Ilmiy axborotnomasi, (7), 273-280.
17. Abduvakhidovna, A. T. (2023). Transformation of Higher Education in Uzbekistan and The Importance of Academic Independence in it. Genius Repository, 24, 99-101.
18. Jumanov, D. T., & Xushboqov, B. (2022). EFFECT OF CRUSHED COTTON ON PRODUCTIVITY. Scientific Impulse, 1(5), 1343-1348.
19. Dilshod, J., & Bobur, K. (2023). PRODUCTION OF ALTERNATIVE DEADLINES FOR PLANTING RICE IN THE PLANT METHOD AS THE MAIN CROP. PROSPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION, 1(14), 109-111.
20. Jumanov, D. T., Kuziboyev, J. B., & Izzatullayev, L. A. (2023). EFFECT OF WATER ON COTTON YIELD. Miasto Przyszłości, 35, 452-456.
21. Jumanov, D. T., Quziboyev, J. B., & Izzatullayev, L. A. (2023). G'O'ZA HOSILDORLIGIDA SUV VA O'G'ITNING O'RNI. Miasto Przyszłości, 35, 457-460.
22. Jumanov, D. T., Kuziboyev, J. B., & Izzatullayev, L. A. (2023). The impact of agrotechnical factors on the productivity of cotton in the context of optimization. In BIO Web of Conferences (Vol. 71, p. 01078). EDP Sciences.
23. Jumanov, D. T., Kuziboyev, J. B., & Izzatullayev, L. A. (2022, December). Agricultural technology and cotton yield. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1112, No. 1, p. 012025). IOP Publishing.
24. Sharofovich, B. O. (2022). WATER-FERTILIZER (NPK) STANDARD IRRIGATION REGIMES OF "BUKHARA-102" AND "PORLOQ-1" COTTON VARIETIES. Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities, 10(12), 816-818.
25. Sharofovich, B. O., & Shapoatovich, M. S. (2023). EFFECT OF POTASSIUM FERTILIZER RATE ON SUNFLOWER YIELD INDICATORS. JOURNAL OF AGRICULTURE AND LIFE SCIENCES, 6(4), 1-6.
26. Sharofovich, B. O., Ishankulovna, A. D., & Erkinovich, K. O. R. (2023). CHANGE OF SOIL VOLUME WEIGHT DEPENDING ON IRRIGATION REGIMES. Gospodarka i Innowacje., 34, 395-396.
27. Sharofovich, B. O., & Abdugadirovich, S. A. (2022). WATER, FERTILIZER (NPK) STANDARD RATIO AND IRRIGATION PROCEDURES OF MEDIUM FIBER "ZARAFSHON" COTTON VARIETY. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 2056-2059.
28. Sharofovich, B. O., & Abdugadirovich, S. A. (2022). WATER AND FERTILIZER REQUIREMENTS OF "PORLOQ-1" COTTON VARIETIES IN WEAKLY SALINITY SOILS. Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 10(12), 2060-2063.

29. Sharofovich, B. O., Abduzhalilovich, K. T., & Nurgabilovich, A. M. (2022). CHANGE OF SOIL VOLUME WEIGHT DEPENDING ON INJECTION PROCEDURES. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(12), 622-623.
30. Azizovna, Y. S. Cognitive Of Students In Language Education Developing Skills. *JournalNX*, 514-516.
31. Azizovna, Y. S. Formation Of Sense Of Respect In Students. *JournalNX*, 1026-1028.
32. Yuldosheva, S. A. (2021). ARTISTICAL PECULIARITIES OF STORY OF "KISSAI IBRAHIM ADHAM". *湖南大学学报 (自然科学版)*, 48(12).
33. Yuldosheva, S. A. STUDY OF FOLKTALE IN LITERATURE AND ITS RELATION TO THE EPIC GENRE.
34. Azizovna, Y. S. (2023). MILLIY DASTUR TALABLARI ASOSIDA O 'ZBEK TILINI O 'QITISHNING SAMARADORLIGI. FAN, TA'LIM VA AMALIYOTNING INTEGRASIYASI, 661-664.
35. Абдираимов, Ш. (2021). Ona tili ta'limida o 'qib tushunish malakasini baholashning nazariy asoslari. *Общество и инновации*, 2(5/S), 119-123.
36. Abdiraimov, S. (2023). O 'QUVCHILARNI AUTENTIK YONDASHUV ASOSIDA BAHOLASH ANAMIYATI. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences*, 2(20), 138-141.
37. Abdiraimov, S. (2023, May). MILLIY KORPUSDAN TEST TOPSHIRIQLARINI TUZISHDA FOYDALANISHNING ANAMIYATI. In «УЗБЕКСКИЕ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫЕ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫЕ ЗДАНИЯ ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЕ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКОЕ СОЗДАНИЕ ВОПРОСЫ" *Международная научно-практическая конференция (Vol. 2, No. 2)*.

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